

Atomic absorption spectrophotometric determination of Pb, Cd, Cu, Mn, Cr, Ni and Fe levels in human hair. Influence of age, hair colour and smoking habit

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Pb, Cd, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni and Cu levels in human hair of 629 healthy subjects exposed to these metals were determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry in relation to age, hair colour and smoking habit. Decrease in metal concentrations were observed in higher age group. Ni, Fe and Cr levels were significantly high at $P < 0.05$ in black hair with respect to white hair. Pb, Cd, Cr and Ni concentrations were significant at $P < 0.05$ in smokers.

Body tissues and fluids can be taken into consideration for evaluating environmental pollution as they harbour toxic and trace metals¹. Hair offers a good way of discerning long term variations in trace element concentrations since (i) the metal concentrations are higher in hair than other human materials and (ii) the specimens can be collected quickly, easily and without stress. Essential trace metals have a wide range of clinical applications. The concentration of metals in human hair is closely linked to personal and environmental factors^{2,3}. Hair colour that is demonstrated by the amounts of melanin pigments in cortex, is a variable that is responsible for trace element levels in it. Age and smoking habits are important parameters influencing the trace metal levels in human hair. In continuation to our studies^{4,5} the present study was undertaken to estimate Pb, Cd, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni and Cu levels in human hair and their variation with three parameters.

Results and discussion

In the present paper we have discussed the variation of metal concentrations in human hair to investigate a

possible correlation between hair metal levels and age, hair colour, smoking habit.

Table 1 reports the mean hair metal concentrations in male subjects of different age groups varying from 11–20 to 51–60 years. In general an increase of levels up to 31–40 years is followed by decrease in higher age groups. Manuwald *et al.*⁶ have reported a significant decrease in lead levels with increasing age. Schroeder and Nason⁷ reported that younger age group showed higher levels of Cu which is in partial agreement with our result. The changing metabolic processes associated with ageing may be responsible for differences in the age group. Except Cu, higher concentrations of Pb, Cd, Mn, Cr, Ni and Fe were obtained in black hair with respect to white hair, of which Ni, Fe and Cr concentrations were found to be significant in this work. Black hair have relatively low hair metal concentration of Pb, Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni and relatively high levels of Mn and Fe in contrast to hair metal levels in mixed hair. Brown hair has been found to contain relatively higher levels of Pb, Cu and Mn and low levels of Fe, Ni, Cd and Cr as compared to hair metal

Table 1. Mean hair metal concentrations as a function of age

Age in yrs.	No. of Samples	Mean concentration of elements (mg/g) \pm S.D.						
		Pb	Cd	Cu	Mn	Cr	Ni	Fe
11–60		11.28 \pm 2.12	0.52 \pm 0.13	10.53 \pm 2.85	8.15 \pm 1.51	48.03 \pm 7.42	26.19 \pm 4.68	188.91 \pm 33.28
11–20	20	7.76 \pm 2.41	0.44 \pm 0.28	9.67 \pm 3.3	6.63 \pm 3.57	46.72 \pm 16.78	24.60 \pm 1.44	133.47 \pm 35.18
21–30	28	10.80 \pm 3.76	0.67 \pm 0.17	8.69 \pm 5.37	62.22 \pm 20.38	22.70 \pm 1.28	22.70 \pm 1.28	189.38 \pm 29.07
31–40	42	13.85 \pm 23.48	0.78 \pm 0.21	13.53 \pm 6.86	57.98 \pm 19.63	32.04 \pm 2.89	32.04 \pm 2.89	214.26 \pm 30.12
41–50	30	10.22 \pm 3.41	0.51 \pm 0.17	7.11 \pm 3.18	45.55 \pm 7.28	26.44 \pm 5.91	26.44 \pm 5.91	177.29 \pm 27.40
51–60	15	13.63 \pm 2.60	0.45 \pm 0.28	7.67 \pm 3.10	39.14 \pm 12.30	30.41 \pm 7.24	30.41 \pm 7.24	154.16 \pm 31.39

levels in black hair. Significant test at $P < 0.05$ between black hair and other hair colour reveal that Pb, Cu, Mn and Pb, Cd, Cr were found to be significant in brown and mixed hair respectively. Schroeder and Nason observed some differences in elemental concentrations in blond, red and black hair. Sturaro *et al.*⁸ have found maximum amount of metals in black hair as observed in our study. Catzias *et al.*⁹ reported that pigmented structures are rich in trace metals including Cu and Mn. Our results for white hair were in support of the above study. The variability of data can be explained due to exogenous contribution on account of pollution in the environment. Besides the pigment content small air spaces and the caliber of the hair shaft also affect the hair colour. A comparison of metal levels in hair of subjects in different age groups with different colour revealed that Cd, Cu, Ni and Fe were higher in black hair in contrast to brown hair in 21–30 years of age group. In 31–40 years age group Pb and Cd concentrations in mixed hair and Cr, Mn, Fe and Ni in black hair were relatively high. In 41–50 years of age group high concentrations were observed for Pb in brown hair, Cd and Mn in black hair, Cu in white hair and Cr, Ni and Fe in mixed hair of the subjects selected for study. Pb, Cd and Ni were high in black hair in contrast to brown hair in 51–60 years of age. As regards smoking parameter, higher concentration of Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, Ni and Cu were observed in smokers with respect to nonsmokers of which Pb, Cd, Cr and Ni were found to be significant. Significant concentration of Pb observed in the hair of smokers can also be attributed to other factors like place of residence of the subjects in vicinity of heavy traffic areas. Ni, Cd and Cr levels were high in smokers relative to nonsmokers in agreement to reported literature¹⁰. The high Cr concentration may be attributed to the Cr content in tobacco leaves which may be incorporated in the same from the soil. Absorption of Ni has been found to be high in smokers as compared to nonsmokers. Smoking was found to be a contributing factor to higher bioaccumulation of Cd in hair¹¹. Smoking does not have a major contribution to Fe concentration which is also confirmed from findings reported in literature. Further the analysis of variance of $P < 0.05$ between smokers and nonsmokers re-

vealed that Cd concentrations manifested in human hair are highly influenced by smoking.

Experimental

Hair samples were digested and sample solutions prepared by the reported method¹². A Perkin-Elmer 250 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was used. A series of standards were prepared in deionized water for instrumental calibration by diluting commercial standards containing 1000 ppm of the metals.

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